

SUSTAINABLE TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE OF CORPORATE ORGANIZATIONS IN SOUTHEAST NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study investigates the effect of Sustainable Total Quality Management (TQM) on the Performance of Corporate Organizations in Southeast Nigeria. Specifically, Customer Focus and Total Employee Involvement—on the performance of corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria. Anchored on Goal-Setting and Quality Improvement theories, the study adopted a quantitative survey research design, drawing responses from 120 staff members across 15 purposively selected organizations. The sample size was determined using Green’s (1991) rule of thumb for regression analysis, ensuring statistical adequacy. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire rated on a 5-point Likert scale, and the instrument’s reliability was confirmed through Cronbach’s Alpha values of 0.81, 0.79, and 0.85 for Customer Focus, Employee Involvement, and Organizational Performance, respectively. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple linear regression. Findings revealed that both Customer Focus ($\beta = 0.37, p = 0.000$) and Total Employee Involvement ($\beta = 0.29, p = 0.002$) significantly and positively influence organizational performance. The regression model accounted for 50% of the variance in performance ($R^2 = 0.50$), and all statistical assumptions were satisfied. These results affirm that embedding sustainable quality management principles enhances performance outcomes in corporate settings. The study concluded that the integration of customer focus and total employee involvement within the STQM framework is crucial for the sustainable development of corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria. The study recommended that Organizations should invest in developing robust customer engagement frameworks.*

Keywords: Management, Performance, Quality, Sustainable, Total

1.1 Introduction

Sustainable Total Quality Management (STQM) is an integrated approach that combines the principles of Total Quality Management (TQM) with sustainability practices to enhance organizational performance while fostering environmental and social responsibility (Ali AlShehail et al., 2021; Shwedeh et al, 2023; Ofoegbu & Eromosele, 2024). TQM is a management philosophy that emphasizes continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and the involvement of all employees (Deming, 1986; Rufus et al, 2022). However, as global awareness of environmental issues and social equity has grown, the need for a more holistic approach that incorporates sustainability into quality management has become increasingly evident (Bohm et al., 2017; Chatterjee et al, 2024).

Total Quality Management emerged in the mid-20th century, primarily focusing on improving processes, reducing waste, and enhancing product quality (Oakland, 2003). The core principles of TQM include customer focus, leadership involvement, employee engagement, process approach, and continuous improvement. These principles aim to create a culture of quality that permeates every level of an organization. The concept of sustainability has gained prominence due to the rising challenges posed by climate change, resource depletion, and social inequalities (Elkington, 1997; Odiboh et al, 2022). Organizations are increasingly recognizing that their operations impact not only their bottom line but also the environment and society at large. Consequently, integrating sustainability into quality management practices is essential for long-term organizational success.

Sustainable Total Quality Management seeks to align quality management initiatives with sustainability goals. This integration involves redefining quality to include not only product excellence but also environmental stewardship and social responsibility (Sroufe, 2003). For example, organizations may implement eco-efficient processes that reduce waste and energy consumption while maintaining high-quality standards (Wagner, 2010). The concept of sustainability, often encapsulated by Elkington's (1997) "Triple Bottom Line" (TBL) – people, planet, and profit – has gained significant traction in recent years. Organizations are now being evaluated not only on their financial performance but also on their environmental impact and social contributions. This shift is driven by increasing stakeholder expectations, stricter environmental regulations, and a growing recognition that sustainable practices can lead to long-term competitive advantages (Porter & Kramer, 2006).

Southeast Nigeria presents a unique context for examining the effects of STQM. The region faces various challenges, including environmental degradation from industrial activities, infrastructural deficits, and socio-economic disparities. Implementing sustainable practices can help businesses comply with increasingly stringent environmental regulations and reduce the risk of penalties. At the same time, there is a growing awareness of the importance of sustainable development among businesses and consumers in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The implementation of Sustainable Total Quality Management (STQM) is increasingly recognized as a vital approach for enhancing the performance of corporate organizations. In Southeast Nigeria,

however, many companies face significant challenges in integrating sustainability into their quality management processes. This region, marked by rapid industrialization and socio-economic disparities, presents a unique context where the potential benefits of STQM remain largely untapped.

Despite the growing awareness of sustainability's importance, many organizations in Southeast Nigeria struggle with inadequate infrastructure, limited access to resources, and a lack of technical expertise. These challenges hinder the effective adoption of STQM principles, which could lead to improved operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and overall organizational performance. Furthermore, there is a notable gap in empirical research examining the specific impact of STQM on corporate performance within this context.

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of Sustainable Total Quality Management on the Performance of Corporate Organizations in Southeast Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

- i. Examine the effect of customer focus on the Performance of Corporate Organizations in Southeast Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of total employee involvement on the Performance of Corporate Organizations in Southeast Nigeria.

1.4 Hypotheses of the study

- i. Customer focus has no significant effect on the Performance of Corporate Organizations in Southeast Nigeria.
- ii. Total employee involvement has no significant effect on the Performance of Corporate Organizations in Southeast Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Total Quality Management

Total Quality Management (TQM) is a comprehensive and integrated management approach that emphasizes the attainment of excellence in organizational performance through continuous improvement, employee empowerment, and customer satisfaction (Awolusi, 2023). It is a holistic philosophy that encompasses all aspects of an organization's operations, from strategic planning to daily activities, with the primary goal of delivering high-quality products or services that meet or exceed customer expectations (Chatterjee et al, 2024). TQM recognizes that quality is not solely the responsibility of the quality control department, but rather a collective responsibility of all employees, from top management to frontline staff. This approach fosters a culture of collaboration, innovation, and learning, where employees are encouraged to identify and solve problems, and where continuous improvement is ingrained in the organization's DNA (Ekemam & Njoku, 2020). By adopting TQM, organizations strive to create a seamless and efficient system that adds value to customers,

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stakeholders, and the organization itself, thereby ensuring long-term sustainability and competitiveness (Kura et al, 2020).

Total quality management is a management approach driven by data that emphasizes the systematic identification, measurement, analysis, and enhancement of organizational processes to achieve significant results. This definition underscores the importance of utilizing statistical tools, benchmarking, and other analytical methods to comprehend and optimize intricate processes, eliminate waste, reduce variability, and improve organizational capabilities (Ofoegbu & Eromosele, 2024). The process-focused nature of TQM acknowledges that organizational performance is predominantly influenced by the effectiveness and efficiency of its underlying processes, and through enhancing these processes, organizations can attain substantial improvements in productivity, quality, and customer satisfaction (Orishede, 2020). By applying TQM principles, organizations can streamline their operations, reduce cycle times, improve supply chain management, and enhance overall organizational agility, thereby positioning themselves for success in today's fast-paced and competitive business environment. This definition emphasizes the critical role of data-driven decision-making, employee involvement, and continuous learning in driving organizational excellence (Permana et al, 2021).

Total Quality Management can also be viewed as a values-based leadership approach that emphasizes the creation of a culture of excellence, driven by shared values, vision, and purpose. This view recognizes that TQM is not just a set of tools or techniques, but a fundamental mindset shift that requires leaders to adopt a long-term perspective, prioritize employee development, and foster an environment of trust, openness, and collaboration (Shwedeh et al, 2023). TQM leaders recognize that organizational success is inextricably linked to the well-being and engagement of their employees, and that by empowering employees to take ownership of quality and improvement initiatives, organizations can unlock the full potential of their human capital (Ughamadu et al, 2024). By embracing TQM, organizations commit to creating a workplace culture characterized by mutual respect, continuous learning, and a relentless pursuit of excellence, thereby ensuring that quality becomes an integral part of the organization's fabric, rather than a separate initiative or programme (Udofia et al, 2021).

Sustainable Total Quality Management

Total quality management (TQM) is a management strategy that aims to improve customer satisfaction and performance by delivering high-quality products and services with the involvement and collaboration of all stakeholders, as well as teamwork by applying quality management techniques and tools (Ali AlShehail et al., 2021). Total quality management is a philosophy that seeks to integrate all organizational functions to meet customer needs and organizational objectives (Alintah-Abel, 2018). TQM is an effective system for integrating the quality development, quality maintenance, and quality improvement efforts of various aspects of a system to enable services at the most economical level and derive satisfaction (Mohammad, 2006). The term "sustainable total quality management" (TQM)

describes how sustainability concepts are incorporated into TQM procedures and practices. In contrast, sustainability takes into account social, environmental, and economic factors and focuses on addressing current demands without sacrificing the capacity of future generations to address their own.

Sustainability in Total Quality Management (TQM) is a topic that has gained prominence due to the growing awareness of environmental and social issues. In this context, the integration of sustainable practices into TQM aims to promote actions that balance meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. In sustainability, strategies for environmental impact reduction are employed. This strategy involves implementing practices and policies that reduce the environmental impact of an organization's operations. By integrating these aspects of sustainability into Total Quality Management, organizations can not only improve their operational efficiency and competitiveness but also contribute to a more sustainable future for future generations. This holistic approach to quality not only benefits the organization but also society as a whole, promoting responsible business practices and preserving natural resources for future generations, LinkedIn Corporation (2024).

Customer Focus

The concept of "customer focus" means meeting the needs and expectations of current and potential customers by developing a comprehensive understanding of customer needs and then delivering perceived value to customers. The expected outcomes of a customer-focused strategy are creating value for customers, which leads to loyal customers, which in turn leads to business profitability. This focus on the customer has slowly been incorporated into manufacturing, but not to the same extent as in services. In the current environment, small and large businesses must become more efficient and cope in a competitive global market where customers' expectations continually increase. Moreover, the "voice of the customer"- his/her suggestions, criticism, complaints, ideas, etc. have to be key elements in a customer-focused strategy, (Sharabi, 2015). Customer focus is fundamental to the TQM philosophy of management for the continuous improvement of products and services of quality to achieve a higher level of organizational performance and competitive advantage (Ashraf, Jaffri, Sharif, & Khan, 2012). Kuo et al., (2009) said that organizations depend on the creation of a quality culture of attaining business intensity through satisfaction of the employees as well as customers and the basic purpose of TQM is to gratify the customers and is articulated by the organization's attempts to grasp current and forthcoming customer wants, and meet customer's necessities in the course of designing and delivering quality products and service. Products and services. Customer-focused planning is the key contributor to improving the performance of an organization. Said, Hui, Taylor, & Othman (2009) believed that total quality management (TQM), the significance of analyzing the queries and objections of customers, getting and losing customers, is one of the major perspectives. The philosophy of TQM believes in the eventual success of organizations in satisfying and fulfilling the requirements of their customers (Temtime & Solomon, 2002).

Total Employee Involvement

Total employee involvement is an organizational methodology and set of management principles that encourage individual contributors, team members, and employees to participate more actively in the problem-solving, decision-making, and planning processes that affect their organization. Within total employee involvement, team members are encouraged to learn more about their organization, contribute ideas, feel more engaged, and look for new opportunities that will help the organization be more competitive and effective. Employee involvement means that every employee is regarded as a unique human being, not just a cog in a machine, and each employee is involved in helping the organization meet its goals. Each employee's input is solicited and valued by his/her management. Employees and management recognize that each employee is involved in running the business. Employee involvement is an empowerment technique where employees participate in actions and decision-making that were traditionally reserved for management. It thus assumes common interests between employees and management. Its main functions are to elicit and grow employee identification and commitment. There are no specific rules to grow involvement (Benazir, 2011).

Employee involvement of any degree results in greater motivation, performance, and a sense of responsibility for the long-term sustained success of the enterprise. Total employee involvement (TEI) is the usual result of a work atmosphere that encourages the energetic participation of every employee in the day-to-day business of the organization (Kumari and Kumari, 2014). With total employee involvement, all team members have the opportunity to help their organization grow, reach its objectives, and overcome obstacles. They can use more of their talents and intellect, along with feeling connected to other team members who are doing the same. Employee involvement enables the organization to have a better insight into the way of functions work and where it can potentially make improvements that would be beneficial for both the organization and employees.

Corporate Organizations

Corporate governance is concerned with the relationship between the internal governance mechanisms of corporations and society's conception of the scope of corporate accountability (Deakin and Slinger, 1997). Corporate governance as defined by Alexander and Matts (2003) refers to corporate decision-making and control, particularly the structure of the board and its working procedures. Becht et al (2002) see the term as the arrangement between the managers of the firm and the owners of the firm, particularly addressing the issue of how managers report the financial health of the firm to the owners. Corporate governance has also been defined by Keasey et al (1998) to include „the structures, processes, cultures, and systems that engender the successful operation of organizations. “ The definition could therefore be centered on how the organization relates to other stakeholders within an environment.

The underlying assumption is that company efficiency is inversely related to the extent to which the interests of owners are diluted by the interests of management in the conduct of business. The corporate governance structure specifies the distribution of rights and responsibilities among the different

participants in the corporation, such as the board, managers, shareholders, and other interested parties, and details the rules and procedures for making decisions on corporate matters (Hebble and Ramaswamy, 2005). The corporate organization idea is the framework and structure that is employed in the formation, management, and operation of a commercial entity. This structure describes the connections among the many parties that are involved in the organization, including employees, executives, stockholders, and other parties.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Goal Setting Theory

Goal-setting theory was postulated by Edwin Locke in 1960, and he asserted that goal setting is fundamentally linked to performance (Locke, 1968). Goal Setting Theory is an intellectual hypothesis of motivation grounded on the assertions that goals do regulate employee behavior. Goal theory postulates a positive link between performance and goal difficulty, with challenging goals eliciting more effort than simple goals. This hypothesis presupposes that behavior is purposeful and that goals focus employees' energies on performing specific tasks (Locke & Latham, 1992). Consequently, the goal-setting theory is an effective strategy for arousing performance by providing feedback, employee involvement, and participation (Locke and Latham 2002).

Quality Improvement Theory

Quality Improvement Theory was brought forth by Deming in 1986. It states that a characteristic of quality management belief is that it places total control of firms directly in the hands of top management. The theory opines that the executive is accountable for the systems and that 80 percent of organizational issues are generated by the system. (Hill,1995). Deming (1986) believed that a systematic approach is the best approach to problem-solving. Under this approach, the Plan Do Check Act cycle (PDCA) was encouraged. PDCA is a concept that aims to continually encourage productivity, thereby bridging the gap between consumers' needs and the production of agricultural industries. Deming's Quality Improvement Theory is significant to this research because TQM practices are utilized in promoting the quality of goods and services through constant advancement, which firms can use to achieve a high level of growth. This notion of quality improvement theory supports the variable on customer focus.

2.3 Empirical Review

Sofijanovska and Zabijakin-Chatleska (2013) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between employee involvement in decision-making and problem-solving, and a firm's performance in the manufacturing sector in the Republic of Macedonia. The study aims to evaluate the relationship between employee involvement in decision-making and problem-solving and the perceived organizational performance of the manufacturing sector in the Republic of Macedonia. A survey research design was used. The results revealed that effective use of employee involvement is positively related to perceived organizational performance.

Asad et al (2016) conducted a study of the relationship between customer focus and organizational performance in telecommunication organizations in Pakistan. The study aims to explore the relationship between seven characteristics of quality culture; employee involvement, senior management leadership, effect of the CEO, supplier partnership, customer focus, teamwork, and open corporate culture with organizational performance and the mediating effect of competitive advantage and the moderating effect of human resources in telecommunication companies in Pakistan. The study was done using content and construct validity. The results revealed that there is a positive and significant association between quality culture and organizational performance of telecom organizations in Pakistan.

Nagarajan (2017) conducted to examination of the factors that influence total employee involvement (TEI) at the organization level of a cutting tool manufacturing company in Bangalore, India. The study aims to discuss the different tools used by the organization for employee engagement, to understand the levels of employee participation in the TEI events, to understand the factors affecting employee participation in the TEI events, and to identify a process for successful implementation of TEI events in a manufacturing company in Bangalore, India. A case study approach was used for this study. The results revealed that several factors resulted in the inability of the organization to achieve the goal of employee participation levels in the TEI events.

Kavulya et al (2018) conducted a study to examine the effect of customer focus strategy on the Performance of savings and credit cooperative organizations (SACCOs) in Kenya. The study aims to evaluate the relationship between customer focus strategy and the performance of SACCOs in Kenya. A cross-sectional survey with a descriptive research design was used for this research. The results revealed that the customer focus strategy has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Saccos in Kenya.

3. Methodology

A quantitative survey was used in the study to investigate the effects of Customer Focus and Total Employee Involvement on the performance of corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria. The study included 1,200 staff members from the 15 organizations chosen for the study. Based on Green's (1991) suggestion, we should have 66 or more respondents, given that there are two predictors. Nevertheless, to ensure the reliability of the results and to replace any missing data, the study ultimately involved 120 participants randomly selected from each department in the selected organizations. The questionnaire used for primary data collection had items that people rated using a 5-point Likert scale. I measured each construct (Customer Focus, Employee Involvement, and Organizational Performance) using four items. Cronbach's Alpha values of 0.81, 0.79, and 0.85 for Customer Focus, Employee Involvement, and Organizational Performance suggest that each scale is internally consistent. Experts reviewed the content to confirm its relevance, and a pilot study helped confirm that the instrument was easy to

understand. For the analysis, SPSS version 29 was used with descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple linear regression.

4. Results

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondent (N=120)

Variable	Category	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	68	56.7%
	Female	52	43.3%
Age	20–29 years	18	15.0%
	30–39 years	42	35.0%
	40–49 years	38	31.7%
	50 years and above	22	18.3%
Educational Qualification	OND/NCE	10	8.3%
	HND/Bachelor's Degree	65	54.2%
	Master's Degree	35	29.2%
	PhD	10	8.3%
Position in Organization	Junior Staff	28	23.3%
	Middle-Level Management	55	45.8%
	Senior Management/Executive	37	30.8%
Years of Work Experience	Less than 5 years	20	16.7%
	5–10 years	45	37.5%
	11–15 years	30	25.0%
	Over 15 years	25	20.8%

The respondents' demographic information in table 1 shows that 56.7% were male and 43.3% were female. Approximately two-thirds of the people surveyed are between 30 and 49 years old. Most likely, the majority of people involved are in the middle of their career, so they have the necessary experience for what they do. It appears from the data that the sample of participants is highly educated. Half of the respondents (54.2%) completed a degree, while 37.5% have a Master's or PhD. Therefore, the participants are equipped to handle questions related to the organization or their studies. The majority of the participants, 76.6%, are in middle-level to top management and executive jobs, suggesting that the study sample consists mostly of those with leadership roles. In addition, over four-fifths (83.3%) have at least five years of experience, proving how mature the respondents are in their careers. All in all, the profile of the demographic group confirms that their input provides reliable results.

Instrument Design

Assume the following items (Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree)

Table 2: Construct and Measurement Item

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Construct	Measurement Item
Customer Focus (CF)	CF1: Our company prioritizes customer feedback. CF2: Customer needs drive our decisions. CF3: I am satisfied with the product/service I received. CF4: I would recommend this company to my friends or colleagues.
Total Employee Involvement (TEI)	TEI1: Employees participate in decision-making. TEI2: Management values employee input TEI3: My contributions are recognized and valued by my supervisor and peers. TEI4: There is a strong sense of teamwork and collaboration in my department.
Organizational Performance (OP)	OP1: Our company meets performance goals. OP2: We continuously improve our results. OP3: The quality of our products/services consistently meets customer expectations. OP4: Our organization encourages innovation and adapts well to changes in the market.

Table 3: Reliability Analysis (Cronbach's Alpha)

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Interpretation
Customer Focus (4 items)	0.81	Acceptable
Employee Involvement (4 items)	0.79	Acceptable
Organizational Performance (4 items)	0.85	Good

Table 3 shows that the results of the reliability test indicate that all three constructs have a Cronbach's Alpha value that is acceptable. Customer Focus which includes 4 questions, has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.81, proving it is reliable. Employee Involvement is made up of 4 items and it also has a satisfactory alpha value of 0.79. The 4 items used to measure Organizational Performance had an alpha value of 0.85 which indicates that the items were very reliable. All in all, these results show that the study's measures are reliable.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 4: Descriptive summary

Construct	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customer Focus	3.87	0.64

Employee Involvement	3.72	0.59
Organizational Performance	3.95	0.61

Table 4 shows that people in the study usually have positive views of all the constructs, as their mean scores are above the middle of the scale. The highest mean score of 3.95 and standard deviation of 0.61 in Organizational Performance suggest that people view the organization's performance as strong and fairly consistent. Customer Focus received an average of 3.87 and a standard deviation of 0.64, suggesting a positive view that is not too variable. Employee Involvement scored 3.72 and had the lowest standard deviation of 0.59 which suggests workers had a slightly less favorable but still positive and steady response. All in all, people agree and see positive aspects in all the constructs.

Table 5: Correlation Matrix (Pearson r)

Construct	CF	TEI	OP
Customer Focus (CF)	1		
Employee Involvement (TEI)	0.58	1	
Organizational Performance (OP)	0.63	0.60	1

Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple regression helps determine the relationship between one dependent variable and several independent variables. It allows us to understand how one independent variable influences the dependent variable, while considering the influence of the other independent variables. Here, Organizational Performance is the outcome that we are studying. The expected factors that will influence the organization's performance are Customer Focus and Employee Involvement. The method can be used to evaluate the impact of Customer Focus and Employee Involvement on changes in Organizational Performance together. The model is presented in the equation below 1;

$$OP = \beta_0 + \beta_1(CF) + \beta_2(TEI) + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Table 6: Regression Coefficients Table

Construct	β (Unstandardized)	Std. Error	t	Sig. (p)
Constant	1.45	0.28	5.18	0.000
Customer Focus	0.37	0.08	4.63	0.000
Employee Involvement	0.29	0.09	3.22	0.000

Table 7: Model Summary

R	R ²	Adj. R ²	F-value	Sig. (p)
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0.71	0.50	0.49	58.32	0.000
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Table 6 shows how the independent variables are related to Organizational Performance. When values for Customer Focus and Employee Involvement are zero, the expected value for Organizational Performance should be 1.45. This is where you should start when measuring your performance. Customer Focus has a coefficient of 0.37, its standard error is 0.08 and the p-value ($p = 0.000$) is highly significant. This means that if Customer Focus goes up by one unit, the organization's performance should rise by 0.37 units while Employee Involvement does not change. The relationship can be considered significant based on statistics. Just like before, the coefficient for Employee Involvement is 0.29, with a standard error of 0.09 and the p-value is also highly significant ($p = 0.000$). As a result, a rise of one unit in Employee Involvement is connected to an increase of 0.29 units in Organizational Performance, with Customer Focus remaining the same. It is also possible to prove this effect using statistical methods. All things considered, Customer Focus and Employee Involvement are important and helpful factors in predicting Organizational Performance.

Table 7 demonstrates that the regression model has a strong relationship ($R=0.71$) between the independent variables and the dependent variable, Organizational Performance. In other words, 50% of the changes in Organizational Performance come from Customer Focus and Employee Involvement. Since the adjusted R-squared is 0.49, the sample size and number of predictors make it reliable to say that the model can explain just over 49% of the changes in organizational performance. Because the regression model has a p-value of 0.000, it is clear that the model is statistically significant. Therefore, using the independent variables as a group, their predictions for Organizational Performance are better than those of a model with no predictors.

Table 8: Assumption Check

Assumption	Method Used	Result
Normality	Histogram /Q-Q plot	Residuals are approximately normal
Linearity	Scatterplot	Relationship is linear
Homoscedasticity	Plots of residuals	Equal variance observed
Multicollinearity	VIF values <2	No multicollinearity

Table 9: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
H01: Customer focus has no significant effect on performance	0.000	Reject H ₀	Customer focus significantly improves organizational performance

H02:	Total	employee	0.002	Reject H ₀	Employee	involvement
involvement	has	no			significantly	improves
significant	effect	on			performance	
performance						

Discussion of Findings

The study explored the impact of Customer Focus and Total Employee Involvement as parts of sustainable total quality management on the performance of corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria, using responses from 120 individuals. Researchers determined the results using multiple linear regression, after checking the data's reliability and correlation. According to the regression analysis, having a customer-focused strategy positively affects the results of corporate organizations. The regression coefficient for Customer Focus is $\beta = 0.37$, and its t-value is 4.63 with a p-value of 0.000, both indicating that Customer Focus is significant. In other words, focusing more on customers is linked to an average improvement of 0.37 units in an organization's performance. The Pearson correlation coefficient between Customer Focus and Organizational Performance was 0.63, which indicates they are moderately to strongly positively related. It confirms that focusing on customers, their needs, and their opinions results in a more efficient and competitive business, which in turn improves the organization's performance. The hypothesis that followed tested how Total Employee Involvement (TEI) affected the company's performance.

The study found that how involved employees are is a valuable predictor, as the regression coefficient is $\beta = 0.29$, the t-value is 3.22, and the p-value is 0.002. The values mean that the relationship between the variables is significant at a 5% level. The total employee involvement and organizational performance show a moderate to strong positive correlation, with $r = 0.60$. This indicates that empowered employees and chances to participate in decision-making are valuable for any organization. The regression model found that 50% of the variation in how an organization performs is due to both Customer Focus and Total Employee Involvement. The model is considered statistically significant because the adjusted R^2 was 0.49, the F-statistic was 58.32, and the p-value was 0.000. As a result, in Southeast Nigeria, Customer Focus and Total Employee Involvement play significant roles in Sustainable Total Quality Management and help improve corporate performance.

The first hypothesis (H₀₁), stating that customer focus has no significant effect on performance, was rejected. The second hypothesis (H₀₂), stating that employee involvement has no significant effect on performance, was also rejected. Both constructs significantly contribute to explaining organizational performance, thereby validating the importance of Sustainable Total Quality Management principles in Nigerian corporate organizations.

5. Conclusion

The implementation of Sustainable Total Quality Management (STQM) in corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria has demonstrated significant potential to enhance overall performance. This study

highlights two critical components of STQM—customer focus and total employee involvement—both of which have been shown to have a profound impact on organizational outcomes in the region. Firstly, the emphasis on customer focus within STQM frameworks has proven essential for improving customer satisfaction and loyalty. Organizations that prioritize understanding and meeting customer needs are better positioned to adapt to market demands, leading to increased competitiveness and profitability. In a region where consumer preferences are rapidly evolving, a strong customer-centric approach allows businesses to differentiate themselves and build lasting relationships with their clients.

Secondly, total employee involvement is a cornerstone of STQM that significantly affects organizational performance. Engaging employees at all levels fosters a culture of collaboration and innovation, leading to enhanced productivity and morale. When employees feel valued and empowered to contribute to quality initiatives, their commitment to the organization strengthens, resulting in improved operational efficiency and reduced turnover rates.

In conclusion, the integration of customer focus and total employee involvement within the STQM framework is crucial for the sustainable development of corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria. By embracing these principles, companies can not only improve their performance metrics but also contribute positively to the socio-economic landscape of the region. Future efforts should aim to facilitate the adoption of STQM practices, ensuring that organizations are equipped to thrive in an increasingly competitive and sustainability-conscious marketplace.

Recommendations

Based on the findings regarding the effect of Sustainable Total Quality Management (STQM) on the performance of corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria, several recommendations can be made to enhance the implementation of STQM practices, particularly focusing on customer focus and total employee involvement:

- i. Organizations should invest in developing robust customer engagement frameworks. This includes regular feedback mechanisms, customer satisfaction surveys, and focus groups to better understand customer needs and preferences. By actively involving customers in the quality improvement process, companies can tailor their offerings more effectively and increase customer loyalty.
- ii. To foster total employee involvement, organizations must prioritize employee training and development. Comprehensive training programs should focus on quality management principles, sustainability practices, and teamwork. Equipping employees with the necessary skills and knowledge will empower them to contribute meaningfully to quality initiatives and organizational goals.

References

Alexander von N and Matts R (2003). Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Firm Performance: Evidence from Finland. Source: RePEc.

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Ali AlShehail, O., Khan, M., & Ajmal, M. (2021). Total quality management and sustainability in the public service sector: the mediating effect of service innovation. *Benchmarking*, 29(2), 382-410.

Alintah-Abel, U (2018). An evaluation of the impact of critical success factors of total quality management on organizational performance in Nigeria. *Sustainable Empirical Environmental Research Journal*. 1(1):27-42.

Asad U, Muhammad M. A and Waqas A (2016). Study of the Relationship between Customer Focus and Organizational Performance in the Telecommunication Organizations of Pakistan. *Information and Knowledge Management Vol . 6, No.12*.

Ashraf, Z., Jaffri, A. M., Sharif, M. T., & Khan, M. A. (2012). Increasing Employee Organizational Commitment by Correlating Goal Setting, Employee Engagement, and Optimism at the Workplace. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(2), 71-77.

Awolusi, O. D. (2023). The effects of total quality management on customer service management in the Nigerian banking industry: an empirical analysis. *International Journal of Management and Network Economics*, 3(1), 57-77.

Becht, M., Bolton, P. & Rosell, A. (2002): *Corporate Governance and Control*, W9371, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge

Benazir Y (2011). A Study on Motivation and Total Employee Involvement. *Akshaya International Journal of Management Studies - Vol. 01 Issue: 02*.

Bohm, S. A., Bock, J., & Riemer, K. (2017). Sustainability in Total Quality Management: A literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142, 1168-1180.

Deming, W. E. (1986). "Out of the Crisis." MIT Press.

Deakin, S., & Slinger, G. (1997). Hostile takeovers, corporate law, and the theory of the firm. *Journal of Law and Society*, 24(1), 124–151.

Ekemam, H. I., & Njoku, B. N. (2020). Total Quality Management (TQM) Practices and Job Performance in Public Service: A Study of Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria. *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 10(2), 192-222.

Elkington, J. (1997). *Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business*. Capstone.

American Research Journal of Economics, Finance and Management

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- Hill, C. W. L. (1995). "International Business: Competing in the Global Marketplace." McGraw-Hill Education.
- Kavulya P.W, Muturi W, Rotich G and Ogollah K (2018). Effect Of Customer Focus Strategy On The Performance Of Saccos In Kenya. *International Journal of Business Strategies Vol . 3, Issue No. 1, pp 1 – 16.*
- Keasey, K., Thompson, S., & Wright, M. (1998). Corporate governance, economic, management, and financial issues. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 13(6), 390–391.
- Kumari, M.K. & Kumari, V.L.P (2014). Influence of employee involvement and organizational culture on productivity: A theoretical concept. *MIJBR-MITS International Journal of Business Research*, 5(27), 423-431.
- Kuo, T., Chang, T.-J., Hung, K., & Lin, M. (2009). Employees' perspective on the effectiveness of ISO 9000 certification: A total quality management framework. *Total Quality Management*, 20(12), 1321–1335.
- Kura, K. M., Abubakar, R. A., & Salleh, N. M. (2020). Entrepreneurial orientation, total quality management, competitive intensity, and performance of SMEs: A resource-based approach. *Journal of Environmental Treatment Techniques*, 8(1), 61-72.
- LinkedIn Corporation (2024). Sustainability in Total Quality Management (TQM). Socratica Learning. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/sustainability-total-quality-management-tqm-socratica-learning-oxo8f/>.
- Locke, E. A. (1968). Toward a theory of task motivation and incentives. *Organizational Behavior & Human Performance*, 3(2), 157–189.
- Locke E and Latham G.P. (1992). A Theory of Goal Setting & Task Performance. *Academy of Management Review* 16(2).
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2002). Building a practically useful theory of goal setting and task motivation: A 35-year odyssey. *American Psychologist*, 57, 705-717.

American Research Journal of Economics, Finance and Management

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Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/ARJEFM>

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- Mohammad, Z. (2006). Nigerian Aviation Sector. Why not a TQM approach? The voicewww.nanka.org.
- Nagarajan R (2017). Determinants of total employee involvement: a case study of a cutting tool company. *International Journal of Business Excellence* 11(2):221-240.
- Oakland, J. S. (2003). *Total Quality Management*. Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Odiboh, O., Nwosu, E., Ekanem, T., & Oyedepo, T. (2022). Public Acuity, Home-made Vehicles and Public Relations in Nigeria. *Journal of South African Business Research*. doi, 10(2022.960007).
- Ofoegbu, W. C., & Eromosele, H. O. (2024). Total quality management and product innovation of manufacturing firms in Rivers State. *IJO-International Journal of Business Management (ISSN 2811-2504)*, 7(03), 01-19.
- Orishede, F. (2020). Impact of strategic planning on organisational growth in the Nigerian manufacturing sector. *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 10(1).
- Permana, A., Purba, H. H., & Rizkiyah, N. D. (2021). A systematic literature review of Total Quality Management (TQM) implementation in the organization. *International Journal of Production Management and Engineering*, 9(1), 25-36.
- Porter, M. E., & Kramer, M. R. (2006). Strategy and Society: The Link Between Competitive Advantage and Corporate Social Responsibility. *Harvard Business Review*, 84(12), 78-92.
- Rufus, A. I., Festus, A. F., & Dada, B. I. (2022). Intellectual capital and organisational performance of the financial sector: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(1), 1-10.
- Said, J., Hui, W. S., Taylor, D., & Othman, R. (2009). Customer-focused strategies and information technology capabilities: Implications for service quality of Malaysian local authorities. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 5(3), 241–256.
- Sharabi, M. (2015). Entry, "Customer Focus", in Su Mi Dahlgaard-Park (Ed.) *Encyclopedia of Quality and the Service Economy*, Sage Pub. (pp. 114-118).
- Shwedeh, F., Aldabbagh, T., Aburayya, A., & Uppilappatta, H. (2023). The impact of harnessing total quality management studies on the performance of smart applications: A study in public and private sectors in the UAE. *Migration Letters*, 20(S12), 83-108.

American Research Journal of Economics, Finance and Management

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Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Sofijanovska, E. & Zabijakin-Chatleska, V. (2013). Employee involvement and organizational performance: Evidence from the manufacturing sector in the Republic of Macedonia. *Traka Journal of Science*, 11(1), 31-36.

Sroufe, R. (2003). Effects of environmental management systems on the operational performance of manufacturing firms. *Journal of Operations Management*, 21(3), 345-357.

Temtine, Z. T., & Solomon, G. H. (2002). Total quality management and the planning behavior of SMEs in developing economies. *The TQM Magazine*, 14(3), 181-191.

Udofia, E. E., Adejare, B. O., Olaore, G. O., & Udofia, E. E. (2021). Direct and indirect impact of quality management on the integrated performance of medium-scale manufacturers. *The TQM Journal*, 33(6), 1589-1609.

Ughamadu, U., Ezeaku, S. N., & Nwogbo, M. O. (2024). Total quality management practices as predictors of teachers' organizational behaviour in public secondary schools in Anambra state. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 10(3), 12-24.

Wagner, M. (2010). The link between sustainability and business performance: A systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 96(2), 55-69.